

THE ROLE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF CRIME PREVENTION

Mukhtorov Jorabek Saidkulovich

Assistant Professor of the Department of Legal Sciences, Candidate of Legal Sciences, Associate Professor of the Higher Education Institute of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11254298>

Annotation: In this article, the importance of crime prevention, the analysis and classification of normative legal documents regulating this field, the importance of preventive measures, the methods of their effective implementation, the role of the neighborhood in the implementation of crime prevention, preventive inspectors, citizens' self-government bodies and the public in crime prevention. cooperation with, measures for effective organization of cooperation and ways of implementation are written on a scientific basis.

Key words: Prevention of crimes, its importance, neighborhood, its activity on prevention of crimes, cooperation, ways of its effective organization.

After the independence of our country, reforms, renewal and great creativity are being implemented by our Government in all spheres. It should be noted that such centuries-old changes are important because they express human interests, restore and develop thousand-year-old noble values and traditions of our people, and increase national pride, dignity, and self-awareness.

Another important aspect of the reforms taking place in our country is that from the first years of our independence, the principle "From a strong state to a strong civil society" was put forward at the initiative of our President. In this process, the ultimate goal was to fundamentally reform the state management system and gradually transfer its tasks to public organizations.

Admittedly, as a result of the implementation of this principle, the activities of the neighborhoods acquired a completely new meaning. The status and legal basis of this unique system of self-governance is initially defined in Article 127 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the General Assembly of our country: it was determined that they have the right to independently solve issues based on the interests of citizens, historical characteristics of development, as well as national values, local customs and traditions, in accordance with the law. This authority is of great importance in the implementation of measures related to the prevention of violations.

With the honor of independence, the fact that "Mahalla" is a national value of the Uzbek people with a long history began to be widely demonstrated. "Mahalla" is an Arabic word that means place, place, space. Historian scholar Narshakhi wrote in his work "History of Bukhara" that 1,100 years ago, the neighborhood was the form of government of the people. Medieval thinkers Mahmud Kashgari in "Devonu lug'otit turk" and Yusuf Khos Hajib in "Kutadgu bilig" wrote about the neighborhood. In ancient times, the neighborhood was also used as a social, administrative-territorial unit. They functioned as a cohesive structure of the team.

The neighborhood is a priceless value that is a support and a support for the wise Uzbek people who have passed the tests of life and have been boiled in the cauldron of various lifestyles, religions, ideologies, and various ideas for centuries. It is a system of self-governance that has survived even in the most tense periods of history, gained people's trust, and expressed the oriental public's point of view.

As our wise ancestors said, "Motherland begins at the threshold." Taking this into account, 1997 - "Year of Human Interests", 1998 - "Year of the Family", 1999 - "Year of Women",

2000 - "Year of Healthy Generation", 2001 - "Year of Mother and Child",

2002 - "Year of Appreciating the Elderly", 2003 "Year of Prosperous Neighborhood",

The naming of 2007 - "Year of Social Protection" and 2012 - "Year of Strong Family" has its own meaning.

Today, we cannot imagine our life without the neighborhood, without the close neighbors who live in this place. It can be said that a neighborhood where true human qualities are polished is literally a **place of harmony**.

Life begins in the neighborhood. The baby will grow up in this place. It is a real happiness for every person to live in a place where neighbors confide in each other, where people can solve their joys and worries, where they speak politely, and who gain respect due to their kindness.

Today's responsibility of the neighborhood is determined by the peace in its territory. The neighborhood has been making a great contribution to the society in matters such as spiritual and educational values, establishing a healthy way of life, raising a mature generation, and ensuring employment of the population.

The neighborhood is a symbol of mutual solidarity, solidarity and kindness formed historically of our people, a place that unites the population of a certain area, a wonderful Motherland.

"It is no coincidence that this unique method of self-management system characteristic of our people has occupied a deep place not only in the language of people since ancient times, but also in their language and in their whole life. We accept the wise saying "Neighborhood is both father and mother" as an expression of this vital truth.

This logic indicates that the neighborhood is the center of education. A well-educated person is usually understood as a model for society, that is, a person with a positive attitude. Such people can refrain from committing an antisocial act as much as possible even in a certain criminogenic situation. This is **one side** of the matter.

Second, the role of the neighborhood in building a strong civil society is incomparable. Because the neighborhood is recognized as a unique institution that knows the way of life and problems of the population, is able to solve them, and unite people in any situation. The main principles of activity here are social justice, democracy, transparency, humanitarianism, independence in solving locally important issues, mutual support based on community. In this

regard, on September 2, 1993, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens" was of great importance.

By November 12, 2010, at the joint meeting of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, said, "Institute of Citizen Self-Government - further improvement of the organizational foundations of neighborhood activities, expansion of its tasks and scope, close cooperation with state authorities and administrative bodies In order to ensure their relations, he noted the expediency of making appropriate amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens".

On this basis, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens" was adopted on April 22, 2013 in a new version. This law makes an effective contribution to increasing the activity of citizens and self-governing bodies in the formation of civil society in our country, strengthening the mutual solidarity of the population, raising their legal consciousness and culture.

Thirdly, 2020 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Decree No. PF-5938 dated February 18 "On measures to improve the socio-spiritual environment in society, further support the neighborhood institution and bring the system of work with family and women to a new level" and the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers dated June 18, 2021 "Citizens themselves The adoption of Resolution No. 380 on additional measures to further improve the activities of self-governing bodies shows that reforms in this area are ongoing.

It can be seen that the activity of citizens' assemblies in our country, especially the so-called self-management - neighborhood institution, is improving day by day. In particular, in the past short period of time, we have implemented an effective cooperation system based on the principle of "**neighborhood - sector - public reception - neighborhood**" to identify and solve population problems, to practically ensure that the neighborhood is a reliable "**bridge**" between the people and the state, to support families and women. complex measures have been implemented in terms of support.

On February 18, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve the socio-spiritual environment in society, further support the neighborhood institution and bring the system of work with family and women to a new level"

By Decree No. PF-5938, the proposal to introduce a new system based on the principle of "**Prosperous and safe neighborhood**" in each neighborhood was approved, providing for the following directions:

turning the neighborhood institution, which is considered a unique social structure of the society, into a real expert and helper of the population, increasing its role and importance;

support women's social activity, strengthen their position in society, strengthen guarantees of protection of their rights and legal interests;

radical reform of organizational and legal mechanisms for ensuring a healthy and stable socio-spiritual environment and peace, harmony and tranquility in society and family;

establishing continuous, systematic cooperation of the neighborhood institute with internal affairs bodies, other state agencies and public organizations;

to further increase the role and position of employees of self-governing bodies of citizens and preventive (senior) inspectors of base points of internal affairs bodies (hereinafter referred to as preventive inspectors), to ensure their independence and practical effectiveness of their powers;

introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the field, as well as proper promotion of the work of employees and improvement of material and technical support.

Also, with this decree, the **Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support of the Republic of Uzbekistan** and its divisions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions, Tashkent city and district (city) were **established**. The main tasks and areas of activity of this ministry in the field of crime prevention were defined as follows:

comprehensive assistance in the full and effective implementation of the principle of **"Prosperous and safe neighborhood"** in society, establishment of close cooperation of citizens with self-governing bodies in improving the socio-spiritual environment in families and neighborhoods;

to strengthen the institution of the family, first of all, to carry out a unified state policy aimed at implementing the idea of **"Healthy family - healthy society"**, organizing targeted assistance to troubled and troubled families;

timely identification of women's problems, provision of socio-legal, psychological and material assistance to women in need of help and who are in a difficult social situation, including women with disabilities;

all-round support in matters of ensuring women's employment, improving working conditions, wide involvement of women, especially young girls in rural areas, in family and private entrepreneurship, handicrafts;

strengthening the place and role of citizens' self-government bodies in society, raising their position in working with the daily problems of the population and implementing effective public control;

strengthening the mutual cooperation of internal affairs bodies, other state agencies and public organizations in matters of ensuring the rule of law in neighborhoods and preventing crimes;

providing financial assistance to lonely elderly people, needing social protection and low-income families, providing legal, methodological and practical assistance in providing social support, effectively using the knowledge and rich life experience of intellectuals to raise the morale of young people, strengthening their patriotism.

According to the decree, it was determined that at least one prevention inspector should be in charge of the service in each neighborhood based on its criminogenic situation and the number of residents.

The Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, together with the Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support, the State Statistics Committee, the General Prosecutor's Office, the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications

Development, in order to categorize neighborhoods based on the criminogenic situation, will collect information on the number of households in each neighborhood and the number of people living in them. Integration of "**Electronic criminal-legal statistics**" into a single information system has been launched.

The following measures have been taken to effectively implement the system based on the principle of "**Prosperous and safe neighborhood**" in the country:

"Centres for preparing young people for family life" were launched in order to implement the standards of a modern exemplary family, to strengthen moral values in families;

"Neighborhood - a place of values" week was organized in order to widely promote national customs, traditions and values;

In order to conduct psychological-corrective and developmental work with children from troubled families, trainings are organized based on the "harmonious family" program;

In order to strengthen families, preserve and develop family values, popularize the life experiences of exemplary families, the contest "Exemplary Family" is being held;

targeted socio-legal, psychological and material assistance is provided to women in need of assistance and who have fallen into a serious social situation, including women with disabilities;

"Spiritual hours" and "Legal knowledge", "Crime prevention", "Fire prevention", "Road safety promotion" days are being held in the neighborhoods by inviting the representatives of the population;

assistance to persons returning from penal institutions is being systematically organized in neighborhoods;

"Protect your child, your home, your Motherland like the apple of your eye!" promotional events are being organized under the slogan;

in order to prevent young people from indulging in various foreign ideas, crimes and offenses among them, public control was established in educational institutions, Internet clubs and night entertainment venues;

on combating human trafficking, forced labor and corruption in neighborhoods and "where there is harmony, there is no place for crime!" promotional events are being held on the subject;

employment of unemployed citizens in the neighborhoods is provided;

"Prosperous and safe neighborhood" republican competition is organized and held among self-governing bodies of citizens;

In order to stabilize the criminal situation in the neighborhoods, training courses are being organized to improve the professional skills of prevention inspectors.

Based on the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated June 18, 2021 No. 380 "On additional measures to further improve the activities of citizens' self-governance bodies", the Model Regulation on the activities of the citizens' assembly was approved. In this regulation, solving issues of local importance based on the interests of citizens in the area, historical characteristics of development, as well as national values, local customs and traditions, increasing their legal culture and social activity, based on the principle of "Prosperous and safe neighborhood" ensuring the stability of the social and spiritual environment was defined as the main goal of the Citizens' Assembly.

Citizens' gathering implements the following measures in the field of crime prevention in **cooperation with internal affairs bodies, including preventive (senior) inspectors:**

1) assist women in need of social protection in entrepreneurship training, development of model business plans and obtaining loans, carry out targeted work with women included in the "Women's register";

2) identify women's problems in a timely manner, conducts individual and specific goal-oriented work with women in severe social situations, including women with disabilities, and organizes social-legal, psychological and material support for them;

In particular, in New Uzbekistan, the value of the individual and human being is given a high place, and the government and society are organized based on the new principle of "**man - society - state**". In a word, the practical result, human benefit, his dignity became the main goal.

If we look at the work carried out in the social sphere over the past years, a new mechanism of working with people in need of social protection and constant assistance such as "**Iron Book**", "**Women's Book**", "**Youth Book**" was introduced. The number of people receiving social benefits has increased almost 1.5 times.

" Iron Book " is a database for registering, identifying, eliminating and monitoring the problems of families with difficult social conditions and living conditions, as well as those under special control by sector leaders.

3) introduces the population, including young people, to national and spiritual values, local customs and traditions and promotes them;

Along with social, economic and political factors, the implementation of reforms in the spiritual and educational spheres is very important in the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan.

We all understand well that if the body of society is economy, then its soul and spirit is spirituality. We rely on these two strong pillars to build a new Uzbekistan, that is, a strong economy based on market principles and a strong spirituality embodying the rich heritage of our ancestors, national and universal ideals. For this purpose, it is necessary to implement the concept of "*New Uzbekistan - an enlightened society*".

*We attach great importance to promoting the humanitarian ideas of our holy Islamic religion, educating our young people who are growing up in the spirit of healthy faith based on the principle of "**enlightenment against ignorance**".*

4) help state authorities to maintain inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance;

It is known that Uzbekistan is a country with great opportunities and wealth. But our greatest wealth is the further strengthening of peace and stability, mutual respect and harmony between representatives of different nationalities and peoples, religious confessions.

It is especially gratifying that today more than 130 representatives of nationalities and peoples live in our country as a single and united family, and that they make a worthy contribution to the development of Uzbekistan with their selfless work.

In the words of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "we are rightly proud of such priceless wealth and direct all the forces and opportunities of our state and society to further strengthen the atmosphere of friendship and harmony in our country."

It should be said that it is important to give priority to the preservation and development of the national identity, mother tongue and culture, religion, customs and traditions of the representatives of all nations and peoples in the state policy.

5) develops and implements necessary measures aimed at social support of unorganized youth in the neighborhood;

6) assist state authorities and management bodies in strengthening law and order;

7) performs public control over the implementation of laws and other legislative documents;

8) takes measures to ensure full and effective implementation of the principle of "prosperous and safe neighborhood";

9) organize effective work on crime prevention in the regions, especially among minors, young people and women;

Threats such as radicalism, extremism, terrorism, human trafficking, drug addiction, which are increasing all over the world, unfortunately, do not escape us either. But I repeat, in our land, where great scholars such as Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Imam Moturidi, who taught the Muslim community, there are people who are lost in this regard, who are given to the ideas of radicalism and extremism?

We will not allow any kind of radicalization in our society, the poisoning of the minds of our youth with destructive foreign ideas, the use of religion for political purposes, and the substitution of ignorance for enlightenment. For this, not only the responsible organizations, but all of us should work together in the family, neighborhood and educational institutions to reveal the humanitarian essence of our holy religion, to educate our children in the spirit of national and universal values

10) together with the centers of social adaptation, implements activities related to social and labor rehabilitation and crime prevention of persons released from places of deprivation of liberty, as well as those under probation supervision;

11) provides information about orphans, children deprived of their parents' care to guardianship and patronage bodies, and also helps to place such children in appropriate state institutions;

12) organizes and coordinates the activities of the public patrol group "Fidokor Youth";

13) support the employment of the population, including young people and women, assist in the employment of persons released from military service, released from penal institutions.

The Deputy Chairman of the Citizens' Assembly for Law and Order issues shall exercise the following powers in order to fulfill the duties assigned to him:

- organizes the maintenance of public order and security in the relevant area, cooperates with other law enforcement bodies and public organizations in this direction;
- investigates the criminogenic situation in the area, the reasons for committing crimes, the conditions that enable them, and based on the results, provides relevant information and suggestions to the chairman of the citizens' meeting, the district (city) internal affairs body, the neighborhood and community support department;
- carries out preventive measures to identify and put an end to violations, to eliminate the causes of their occurrence and the conditions that allow it, and to carry out preventive work with persons prone to committing violations;
- keeps preventive records, including records of offenses, persons who committed them and victims of offenses in accordance with the procedure established by legislation, implements measures aimed at providing them with legal, social, psychological, medical, pedagogical and other types of assistance;
- involving representatives of state bodies and organizations, civil society institutions, conducts activities on crime prevention, raising legal consciousness and culture of citizens, instilling in them a sense of respect for the law;

"Salvation is in education,
salvation is in upbringing,
salvation is in knowledge.

Because all good goals are achieved thanks to education and upbringing.

These words of our enlightened grandfathers should become practical actions of our deputies and senators, political parties, local councils, the entire state apparatus, and the general public.

- makes submissions to the heads of state bodies, public and other organizations on the causes of violations and the elimination of the conditions that enable them;
- identifies and keeps records of persons who have left their place of permanent residence for a long period of time, regularly works with relatives to determine the places and periods of their stay abroad, carries out preventive work with persons who have returned from a long period of stay abroad;
- based on the results of the work of the partner law enforcement officers involved in curbing crimes in neighborhoods with a severe criminogenic situation, makes suggestions on their motivation and solving the issue of disciplinary liability;
- studies every family in the area, identifies troubled families and conducts preventive work with them, including helping to solve their household and other problematic issues with official organizations;
- supervises the persons sentenced to a criminal sentence not related to the deprivation of liberty, as well as the persons subject to a precautionary measure not related to imprisonment, who are in the charge of the probation service of the internal affairs bodies, in accordance with the procedure established by the legislation, conducts preventive work with them;

- supervises the behavior of persons sentenced to imprisonment for the first time and who are placed under direct probation control with a lighter sentence, help them to socialize and prevent them from re-offending;

- implements educational and preventive measures for persons released from penal institutions and placed under administrative control, monitors compliance with the restrictions stipulated by legislation;

- identifies persons who are not registered according to their place of permanent residence or place of temporary residence or who live in violation of the requirements of the passport-visa regime in any other way, checks the existence of contracts for the rent of citizens' residences or their free use;

- takes appropriate measures to ensure compliance with the safety rules for the use of the housing fund and areas around the houses, including the safety rules for the use of attics and basements of multi-storey buildings and other additional buildings and rooms by the owners of residences and housing owners' associations;

- takes measures to identify unoccupied dwellings and control their preservation in accordance with the procedure established by the legislation;

- guardianship and patronage bodies are assisted in the placement of orphans and children left without parental care;

- in order to prevent the repeated occurrence of violence against women and to ensure the safety of the victim of violence, implements measures aimed at providing mental and social support to a person in changing his behavior prone to violence, a person who has committed violence or is prone to committing it arranges to undergo a correctional program for changing his character;

- reports on the state of crime prevention and crime prevention every month to the council of citizens' assembly, at least once every quarter to the assembly of citizens (meeting of citizens' representatives), makes relevant proposals;

- consultant on youth issues, organizes and coordinates the activities of the public patrol group "Selfless Youth";

- issues protection warrants to women victims of oppression and violence and ensures its execution;

- in the exercise of his authority, the deputy chairman of the citizens' assembly for law and order issues shall check the identity documents of citizens, if there are reasons to suspect that they have prohibited items and tools, conduct a personal inspection and inspect their belongings, which were the weapon or direct object of the offense in case of detection of goods and documents, it may take them away in the manner established by the legislation.

In particular, this structure works in cooperation with the sub-systems of state and non-governmental non-profit organizations to improve the social and moral environment in the region, prevent violations and crimes, maintain public order, increase vigilance and awareness of citizens, and ensure peace, tranquility and stability. After all, anti-social behavior in a person arises and is formed in small environments such as family, neighborhood, work teams. In a word, all negative events, including crime, arise in conditions of spiritual poverty and lack of education.

Based on this conclusion, it can be said that in order to strengthen the work in the area of public safety, crime prevention and crime fighting in the neighborhood, the public patrol

group "Secretary Youth" was formed from among conscripts, higher military educational institutions and candidates for internal affairs bodies.

After all, it is necessary to fight against crime, including the prevention of crimes, effective organization of its prevention, and ensuring the rule of law in society, not only the task of internal affairs bodies or other bodies that carry out the prevention of crimes, but also the important task of every citizen, neighborhood, and the public. However, everyone is equally responsible for fighting and preventing crime in order to live peacefully and prosperously in the society.

In particular, as a result of the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses" dated May 14, 2014, citizens' assembly and prevention inspectors are responsible for ensuring peace and tranquility in neighborhoods, human rights and freedoms, and the safety of citizens, as well as prevention of offenses, protection of the growing young generation from various threats. an effective system of cooperation between

In Article 21 of this law, the participation of citizens' self-governing bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations and citizens in the prevention of crimes, in particular, in the provision of public order in the relevant area, including the organization of accounting for the arrival and departure of citizens, the prevention of lack of control and crimes among minors, and their rights assistance to law enforcement agencies in cases of protection is clearly stated.

In general, along with the employees of internal affairs bodies, citizens' self-government bodies have a great contribution to maintaining peace and tranquility in our country and ensuring its stability. It is not for nothing that our people say that if the family is peaceful, the neighborhood is peaceful, and the peace of the neighborhood is the peace of the country.

After all, as the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoev, said, "we will make all reforms and actions together with the society. All of us must serve our people as one force and power."

Our grandfather Imam Moturidi:

"Live in sympathy with the country, so that the people will always be with you" should be imprinted in the mind, heart and actions of every minister and every leader.

In short, in our country, the place and role of the neighborhood in the socio-political life of society, especially in the implementation of crime prevention, is very high. In addition, the neighborhoods that glorify our national values and traditions, which have become a place of solidarity and exemplary work, are worthy of envy. Our grandfather, Alisher Navoi, in his work "Hayrat-ul Abror" defined "Neighborhood - a town within a city",

and also emphasizes that there is respect and equality between the residents of the neighborhood, and care is valued in the relationship between the rich and the poor.

It should be emphasized that citizens' assemblies effectively perform tasks within their powers, including the proper organization of their cooperation with other subordinate agencies, the systematic implementation of assistance to the family, women and the elderly, and the effectiveness of the measures taken for the early prevention of crimes. serves to improve the socio-spiritual environment in the society and ensure the rule of law.

Based on the above, it should be noted that the neighborhood is the basis and support of civil society. Because the neighborhood's contribution to strengthening peace and harmony in our country cannot be compared with anything. The fact that Uzbek qualities such as love for the motherland, harmony, good neighborliness, kindness, and respect for elders are formed in the neighborhoods increases the trust of the society towards this unique institution.

